

WP2: National policy, legal and service frameworks

Psychosocial Support for Promoting Mental Health and Well-being among
Adolescent Young Carers in Europe: ME-We project, Grant Agreement number
754702

Country-specific report (case study) The Netherlands

Source: <https://pixabay.com>

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Categories	Results
Specific legislation	In the Netherlands, no specific legislation protecting and supporting young carers ‘jonge mantelzorgers’ and their families exists.
Non-specific legislation National level	<p>Child protection</p> <p>Child protection orders are regulated in the Dutch Civil Code Book 1 Law of Persons and Family Law Section 1.14.4 Custodial control remedies for minors Article 1:254 Grounds for ordering custodial control over minors to Article 1:278 Request for a restoration of parental authority; probationary period http://www.dutchcivillaw.com/civilcodebook01.htm</p> <p>To initiate a child protection order the municipality (under the Child and Youth Act (Jeugdwet)) or Veilig Thuis* (under the Mandatory Reporting Code Act https://www.government.nl/documents/reports/2013/03/14/model-reporting-code-domestic-violence-and-child-abuse and Wmo) has to request an investigation by the Child Care and Protection Board (Raad voor de Kinderbescherming) to investigate a child protection order and file a request at the children’s court.</p> <p>*Veilig Thuis= a certified institution or a youth assistance provider appointed by the municipal authorities (see brochure Child Care and Protection Board; Raad voor de Kinderbescherming; https://www.kinderbescherming.nl/documenten/brochures/2015/01/01/brochure-about-the-child-care-and-protection-board-2015)</p> <p>Targeted age group: minors (<18)</p> <p>The Social Support Act (Wet maatschappelijke ondersteuning, Wmo 2015), January 2015 https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0035362/2018-08-01</p> <p>Under the Wmo, local authorities support people who have difficulty participating in society or who cannot take care of themselves or have a need for sheltered accommodation or support.</p> <p>Municipalities are responsible for the appreciation and recognition of informal caregivers within their municipality</p>

Targeted age group: 18 years and older (adults).

The Child and Youth Act (Jeugdwet) January 2015, Article 2.1 <https://zoek.officielebekendmakingen.nl/stb-2014-105.html>

Local municipalities are responsible for decreasing the number of children in specialised care, increasing preventive and early intervention support, and promoting the use of social networks.

Article 2.1

The municipal policy on prevention, youth assistance, child protection measures and juvenile rehabilitation and the implementation of youth assistance, child protection measures and juvenile rehabilitation is aimed at (amongst other things):

- the prevention and early identification of and early intervention in growing and upbringing problems, psychological problems and disorders;
- promoting the parenting skills of the parents, so that they are able to bear their responsibility for the upbringing and growing up of young people;
- engaging, restoring and strengthening the potential and the problem-solving capacity of the young person, his parents and the persons belonging to their social environment, using their own input where possible;
- promoting the safety of the young person in the parenting situation in which he / she grows up;
- integral help to the youngster and his parents, if there are multiple problems, and
- the establishment and implementation of family group plans and the provision of help on the basis of family group plans

Targeted age group: children (up to 18 , which may be extended in some circumstances to 23).

The Mandatory Protocol (Domestic Violence and Child Abuse) Act Organisations are required by law to have a domestic violence and child abuse protocol in place.

Legal framework for the protocol

The mandatory use of the protocol is specified in the Act. Organisations in the following sectors are required by law to have a domestic violence and child abuse protocol in place: health care; education; child care; social support; youth care; the criminal justice system. This requirement does not apply to volunteer organisations. Volunteer organisations are, of course, allowed to develop their own step-by-step plan.”

	<p>The law stipulates that a reporting code must include a 'Child Check' (Kind Check) in the case of certain adult clients.</p> <p>Compulsory Education Act 1969 (Leerplichtwet 1969) https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0002628/2018-07-28 and The Compulsory Education Act 2007, Article 4a and 4b</p> <p>Targeted age group: Students have to attend school until they are 18 or they have obtained a basic qualification.</p>
<p>Non-specific legislation Regional level</p>	<p>None mentioned</p>
<p>Enactment of legislation National level</p>	<p>The Child and Youth Act (Jeugdwet) January 2015 Whether young carers are receiving any support through existing legislation is not clear. Current support for young carers is likely to be very inconsistent and is dependent upon municipalities and the viewpoints and actions of individuals; children, parents and professionals.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Young carers currently could be supported through either the voluntary sector or under child protection measures. - Significant youth support exists, however there may not be sufficient attention given to supporting young carers. - Parenting support is available. - The first evaluation of the youth law has been published. https://publicaties.zonmw.nl/eerste-evaluatie-jeugdwet/ <p>Social Support Act (Wet maatschappelijke ondersteuning, Wmo 2015)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Parents are able to get respite care whilst their child is being looked after. <p>Compulsory Education Act 1969 (Leerplichtwet 1969) and The Compulsory Education Act 2007</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Compulsory Education Act is implemented by municipal authorities. The Act requires each municipality to have one sworn attendance officer. - Parents are responsible under the law to ensure their children attend school and sanctions can be imposed under criminal law <p>Child protection measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A supervision order with or without an out of-home placement, can be enforced by the juvenile court; the parents remain responsible for the care of their child, but they are obliged to follow the advice of the guardian. - Youth support for the child can be deployed which often includes parenting support.

	<p>Increasing awareness Project Group National Implementation Impulse Child Check in mental health care https://kindcheck-ggz.nl/ A national project group works with mental health care providers. Its aim is to increase awareness of adolescent young carers in mental health care using the (Child Check) 'Kind Check GGZ'</p>
<p>Enactment of legislation Regional level</p>	<p>The project Jong & Zorgend (Young and Caring) provided by care support organisation Mantelzorg & Meer (Informal care & More). The project provides support for AYCs and was initiated by four municipalities (Aalsmeer, Amstelveen, Haarlemmermeer en Uithoorn in the Province of North Holland). The project is financed by the Province of North Holland within the framework of the Regionale Sociale Agenda (Regional Social Agenda). Within this framework, the province implements policy within the social domain, partly on the basis of its statutory duty to support municipalities in the implementation of the Social Support Act (Wmo).</p>
<p>Changes in legislation</p>	<p>Many different ministries were involved in introducing the Child and Youth Act (Jeugdwet) January 2015 which has recently brought about a huge decentralization and transformation of the Dutch youth care system. Responsibilities have not only been decentralised to the 393 municipalities, but there has been a transformation of approach with a focus now on: the role of the family and social networks in the care process, prevention and a better coordination and integration of services. Further decentralisation has taken place at the same time, with the Social Support Act (Wmo, 2015), and the Participation Act (Participatiewet, 2015) being introduced in January 2015.</p>
<p>Specific policy and service frameworks national level</p>	<p>There are no specific policy and service frameworks for young or adolescent young carers.</p>
<p>Specific policy and service frameworks local level</p>	<p>None mentioned</p>
<p>Non-specific policy and service frameworks National level</p>	<p>Wet meldcode huiselijk geweld en kindermishandeling (Domestic violence and child abuse protocol) https://www.government.nl/topics/domestic-violence/domestic-violence-and-child-abuse-protocol and https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0033723/2018-07-28 This is the legal basis of the Child Check (Kind Check)</p> <p>Child check instructions Organisations need to have instructions in place before a child check can be carried out. A child check is when professionals check whether a family has children and, if so, whether those children are safe. For instance, when a parent has a psychiatric</p>

disorder or addiction. The government is currently compiling basic guidelines for the child check.

Decision compulsory reporting code domestic violence and child abuse

<https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0033723/2018-07-28>

Laying down the minimum requirements for the compulsory reporting code for domestic violence and child abuse (Decision compulsory reporting code domestic violence and child abuse)

Toolkit Mantelzorg

<https://www.lhv.nl/service/toolkit-mantelzorg%20>

The Toolkit Mantelzorg is an advice of the Association for Dutch General Practitioners for general practitioners to pay attention to informal carers, including young carers (under 18 years old).

NHG Guidelines

<https://guidelines.nhg.org/>

The Dutch College of General Practitioners (the scientific society of Dutch general practitioners) publishes clinical practice guidelines, of which some specifically refer to informal care. For example, the clinical guideline Dementia states that GP's need to assess the needs of carers.

The Dutch Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sports launched three programs (Spring to Autumn 2018), with the aim that all disabled people and their significant others/relatives should be able to participate in society in line with their preferences.

Onbeperkt meedoen! 'Participating without limits' and Zorg voor de jeugd 'Care for the youth' focus primarily on adults or youth with disabilities.

The third program addresses both patients and their family. In the field of disabled care this program (Vol-waardig Leven 'A full and fulfilling life') for patients using long-term care and their relatives was developed by the national government in the Netherlands (launched October 2018). Brothers and sisters of a disabled child are explicitly mentioned. It is stated specifically that the family (including children) need to be visible within the healthcare sector and society at large and that their needs should be addressed. The importance of information is mentioned.

<https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten-ten-rapporten/2018/09/30/programma-volwaardig-leven>

House of Representatives (2017) passed a motion on the accessibility of psychological aid to students. As a result, Minister

	<p>Ingrid van Engelshoven called together the VSNU (Universities) and VH (Universities of Applied Science), the student associations LSVb and ISO and the Expertise Center for Disability and Education to discuss a joint ambition for students who need extra support. The minister decided to set up a student welfare working group. Bottlenecks have been identified and 5 aims have been developed. Focus is not only on students with psychological complaints, but also on students with informal care tasks, young parents and pregnant students, students in gender transition and students with a disability. The results of a kick off meeting 17 september 2018 will be included in a joint ambition to be presented in October in a letter from the Minister to the House of Representatives https://www.handicap-studie.nl/89_1482_Start_aanpak_studentenwelzijn.aspx Framework targeted at universities, (18+)</p> <p>Guidelines Children of Parents with Mental Problems (KOPP) for youth care and youth protection http://richtlijnenjeugdhulp.nl/kopp/ On the initiative of the Netherlands Institute of Psychologists (NIP), the Dutch association of pedagogues and educationalists (NVO) and the Professional Association of Professionals in Social Work (BPSW), the Program Guidelines youth aid and youth protection is developing and supporting the introduction of guidelines for youth professionals. There are currently 14 guidelines available.</p> <p>United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) https://www.unicef.org.uk/what-we-do/un-convention-child-rights/ The Netherlands has ratified the Convention on the Rights of the Child. The Children's' Ombudsman (https://www.dekinderombudsman.nl/241/english/) checks whether the rights of the child are respected. One of the rights in the Convention on the Rights of the Child is the right to education. In the Netherlands, the right to education is enacted (in national law) through the Compulsory Education Act. Targeted age group: minors (<18)</p>
<p>Non-specific policy and service frameworks Local level</p>	<p>None mentioned</p>
<p>Enactment of policy and service frameworks National level</p>	<p>A national website for diverse groups (including professionals, children, parents, municipalities) on the topic of children with parents with psychological problems (KOPP) or addiction problems (KVO) with information on interventions and guidance on how to cooperate with other organisations in this field. https://www.koppkvo.nl/ and https://www.trimbos.nl/themas/kopp-kvo/landelijk-platform-kopp-kvo</p>

<p>Enactment of policy and service frameworks Regional level</p>	<p>Municipalities have been developing and promoting support programs for AYCs: In Amsterdam for example, support for young carers is promoted by the municipality https://www.amsterdam.nl/zorg-ondersteuning/ondersteuning/mantelzorg-gewoon/jong-mantelzorgen/waar-terecht/</p>
<p>Enactment of policy and service frameworks Local level</p>	<p>None mentioned</p>
<p>Changes in policy and service frameworks</p>	<p>None mentioned</p>
<p>Recognition of young carers (only available on regional level)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Young carers are not specifically defined in the law and young informal caregivers do not recognise themselves as `young carers`. - There is a general lack of recognition and awareness of young carers that is children who have care responsibilities even amongst professionals. However, more attention is now being given to the subject with stories about young carers which are being highlighted in the media and voluntary agencies recognising when children have caring responsibilities. - There is awareness of the psychological impacts on children who have parents with psychological or addiction issues (children of parents with mental (KOPP) or addiction problems (KVO)) and a taskforce has been set up to address this.
<p>Key strengths</p>	<p>The new Child and Youth Act (Jeugdwet) 2015 has brought new clarity and goals for supporting children, youth and families and the extent to which these goals are being met. Responsibility for delivering this has been devolved to the municipalities who have more insight into what the problems are within their municipality and they can respond better.</p> <p>A first evaluation of the Act has been undertaken https://publicaties.zonmw.nl/eerste-evaluatie-jeugdwet/</p>
<p>Key limitations National level / local level</p>	<p>General limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Young carers are not explicitly mentioned in this law which is `the big problem` - There are challenges around the transition period (in all areas of youth rights) and connecting the support as children become adults. - There are multiple protocols and guidelines being used in different areas of support such as in health, mental health care as well as in youth care. Care is segmented. An integrated approach is lacking, (for example around hospital discharge). <p>Limitations to the Child and Youth Act (Jeugdwet) 2015</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decentralisation of responsibilities to the municipalities, has led to inconsistent support with differences between municipalities. Municipalities can decide for themselves what constitutes basic care provision. - There have been budget cuts for youth support and monitoring of goals and outcomes is not yet in order. - There is a lack of information and guidance for parents to support them and their children.
<p>Evaluation of the current situation National level / Local level</p>	<p>Legislative changes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The legislative changes are recent and the legislation may not have embedded smoothly everywhere and there is some dissatisfaction about how effective the new system is. <p>Recognition of the issue and awareness of young carers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is recognition that there are significant numbers of young carers. - In practice few professionals identifying them and often the link is not made between a parent be ill or disabled and a child being a young carer. More recognition of the issue of young carers is needed. - There is some knowledge and understanding about the issue of young carers. Although awareness is rising, this is primarily with regards to children caring for someone with mental ill-health. For these children there are evaluated interventions, but focused on the prevention of psychological issues as a consequence of their parents' condition, rather than as a consequence of their caring roles. For young carers in general the awareness remains low, even with doctors and there is a lack of guidance for parents. <p>How young carers are perceived</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There may be opposing views about the agency of children; whether or not children can choose to be taking on caring roles in the first place and at what age. - The reason why the support needs of adolescent young carers may not have been addressed in legislation or policy may be due to the perception of children and young people. Young people are seen as being children for perhaps longer than in some countries (such as African countries for example) and there is therefore a focus on their protection as children, which may not accommodate the possibility that as they become older and independent they may require support as informal carers. <p>Lack of consistency across the country</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Some initiatives exist, but the legal frameworks and policies do not. Where initiatives exist, they are not mapped out and may not be known about by families. - Support is not consistent across the country, but is dependent upon the local situation, local priorities and individuals. <p>Child protection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For some young carers child protection measures will be appropriate. Where they are appropriate, they should be

	<p>used.</p> <p>Support focused on parents – not on children</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A lot of money is seen as going into care, however the money may not be necessarily be getting to all those who need it. For example, it may be going directly to those who are disabled, but not to the whole family. - In families where there is parental illness or disability or where or where there are disabled or ill siblings, support is currently focused on parents rather than on the support needs of other children who might be carers. Only when it is the child themselves who has the problem is the support child focused, with ‘one child: one plan’. - Children with caring responsibilities are not being noticed. Young carers are not recognising themselves as carers making it difficult for municipalities to know who the young carers are in their area. - Children are not asked for their opinions and so young carers are not being noticed and identified as having support needs [VALIDATE] - Children will not always be aware of their rights and support available. Parents are not receiving guidance. - Currently there are issues with privacy and sharing information. Children may not be given information about the situation of their parent for example or other information that would be helpful. Support may be given, but it is not systematic. <p>Identification of young carers and education law</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Young carers could be identified and supported if school attendance is disrupted, however this does not appear to be happening in a preventative manner. Teachers may not be aware of the family situations of their pupils and there is currently not a consistent approach to identifying young carers by schools.
<p>Attitudes to existing policy responses</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Legislation is necessary in order to drive forward policies for young carers. - Young carers under 18 should be viewed differently from adult carers over 18 years old since they have different legal positions. - The recent changes in youth legislation have not yet yielded results but have led to increased bureaucracy and less available funding. One positive is that support can continue until aged 23. - Child protection measures: In some circumstances, being a young carer might necessitate initiating child protection measures. - Approaches to supporting young carers will in the future probably come through family care under the Wmo. - A lack of policy frameworks and laws could be explained by a country ‘not noticing’ young carers. - The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) is viewed as very important because it is the first treaty worldwide, where it sums up all the rights for the children and because there is no other treaty worldwide that is ratified by nearly all countries. Several articles particularly highlighted such as Articles 12, 17 and 18 and that General Comment (No. 20, 2016) may have particular relevance.

	<p>https://tbinternet.ohchr.org/_layouts/treatybodyexternal/Download.aspx?symbolno=CRC%2fC%2fGC%2f20&Lang=en</p>
<p>Suggested changes</p>	<p>General suggestions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Comparisons should be made with what is being done in other countries for example research undertaken as to how the ‘Care Act’ in the England came about. - Young carers will have many ideas and should be consulted. - Good projects and initiatives should be researched. - A multi-faceted approach is necessary that includes training and education - More education about young carers and how to support families should take place in schools and in universities. <p>Legislation and policy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Legislation and policy is important for laying the foundations and is necessary to bring about uniformity. This should then be enacted in different ways to accommodate the needs of such a diverse group. - Discussions about young carers should be integrated with discussions about adult informal carers. - Using a minimalist approach in order to keep things as normal as possible for young carers - The law (The Child and Youth Act (Jeugdwet) should be changed to a more prescriptive entitlement of provision of care - Not to separate the support for different groups of young carers, but rather have a more universal approach, along the lines of the Care Act in the UK. When you are working with an adult with care needs, the children are also assessed. - Take a collaborate approach towards policy making. <p>Approaches</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A preventative approach should be taken to lessen negative impacts and need for specialist support. ‘Health insurers should go for prevention’. [VALIDATE meaning] - Support can be from multiple agencies. - The needs of young carers need to be assessed and support provided to meet those needs. - Children and families should be given information about their particular situation and support available to them. - Initiatives should be mapped and children and families informed about them - Information and support modules could be developed for young carers. - Use technology (e.g. an App) to help reduce negative impacts.
<p>Future goals and hopes</p>	<p>Inappropriate caring roles</p>

National / local level	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Young carers should be protected against inappropriate caring and attention should also be given to what the rights should be. <p>Legislation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- In the future, legislation is seen as important for ‘laying the foundations’.- International Cooperation Agency of the Association of Netherlands Municipalities (VNG) http://www.vng-international.nl/ could be involved to draw up legislation along the lines of the Care Act in England. Current social care legislation could be amended to include the assessment of the needs of young carers as in the UK. <p>Recognition and understanding</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- More recognition and understanding is needed about this group of children and young people, including the number of young carers, the impacts of caring roles, their needs and their rights and the support available to them.- A broad awareness is needed among all those working with young people. Professionals need training about who young carers are and the impacts of caring. Students also need to be made aware of the issue through the education curriculum. <p>A preventative approach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Since the Netherlands is moving increasingly towards a preventative model of support it is hoped that children should also be part of discussion and specifically that preventative care for young carers would be helpful.- Identification of young carers needs to improve and new approaches need to be employed.- Schools should also play a key role as part of a preventative approach by identifying and assessing the needs of young carers. Discussion of subjects in schools, including informal caring should be normal. Practice developed for other groups – such as pupils with impaired hearing – could followed. <p>A collaborative approach and improved integrated working</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Support can be from multiple agencies and collaboration between agencies would be a better approach. Improved integrated working would for example improve support for young carers at the transition period, when becoming adults. <p>Family focused approach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- There is hope for a more family focused approach and more of a defined legislation and directives such as in the UK.- Families should be assessed including assessment of the needs of children. Family support should be developed by enlarging their network of support.- The issue should be understood by all professionals and it should be standard practice that the issue is acknowledged, talked about with families and followed up with support.- Families to be signposted to local support by Neighbourhood teams could play a really supportive role by signposting carers to local support
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- Families to be strengthened by having support organised into a network of support
- The whole family should be supported. Young carers should be seen and involved in a care plan. Their opinions need to be sought.

Assessing the needs of young carers

- A more systematic way of understanding young carers' needs to avoid pupils to have repeating their story multiple times.
- The needs of young carers need to be assessed and support in place to address the different needs. E.g. Support for young carers with their education.
- When there is a person with health problems in the family there should always be a check for how the children are doing and what their needs are.

Support and Information for young carers

- Young carers need information at different points in their life. They should be informed about what support they can get and how to access it. In each municipality there could be a support point for young carers.
- Legislation to increase visibility of support for example by explicitly stating for example that this support is available for carers.

Improved transition work

- Special attention should be taken to protect adolescent young carers as they are at a vulnerable period and developing their own identity. Just because they have reached a particular age, they should not be burdened by caring roles.